
Dissecting the drug-receptor interaction with the Klopman-Peradejordi-Gómez (KPG) method. I. The interaction of 2,5-dimethoxyphenethylamines and their N-2-methoxybenzyl-substituted analogs with 5-HT_{1A} serotonin receptors

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Abstract We studied the relationships between electronic structure and 5-HT_{1A} receptor binding affinity of a group of 2,5-dimethoxyphenethylamines and their N-2-methoxybenzyl-substituted analogs. The novelty of this study is that we analyzed four hypothesis about the mode of binding, leading to four different common skeletons. For all cases statistically significant equations were obtained, each one leading to a partial interaction pharmacophore. The integration of all the results into a unique pharmacophore that provides more detailed information about the mode of binding of these molecules to the 5-HT_{1A} receptor.

Keywords 5-HT_{1A}, serotonin, QSAR, common skeleton, DFT, electronic structure, Phenethylamines, N-2-methoxyphenethylamines, Pharmacophore

Introduction

The Klopman-Peradejordi-Gómez (KPG) method relating electronic structure and biological activity is, as far as we know, the only member of the class of model-based methods. It starts from the statistical mechanical definition of the equilibrium constant [1]. Then, by applying physically reasonable hypotheses it produces a relationship between local atomic reactivity indices and the drug-site equilibrium constant. This model has been enlarged through the years. The first version was proposed by Peradejordi et al. including the treatment of the drug-site interaction energy [2]. Later the contribution of the molecular partition functions was analyzed [1]. After this, the drug-site interaction energy was again analyzed giving origin to a group of reactivity indices related to the Molecular Orbitals (MOs) [3]. The next step was the analysis of the molecular rotational partition function giving origin to the orientational parameters [4]. During year 2013 a new analysis of the drug-site interaction energy gave origin to local atomic indices such as local atomic hardness, local atomic softness, local atomic electrophilicity, etc. [5, 6]. These local atomic indices looked like the ones coming from conceptual density functional theory but they are conceptually different from them because their units are the same than the global indices. The last development was the guess, based on studies published during years 1965-1975, that this equation can be applied to any biological activity, provided that all molecules have the same action mechanism [7]. The results of the application of this method have been excellent when applied to several molecular systems and biological activities (see [8-22] and references therein). Considering that the method has been explained with detail in many papers and one freely available book, we refer the reader to the literature (all the papers and the book can be found at www.researchgate.net).

The practical application of the KPG method is difficult by the fact that no research group has ever published a paper with enough molecules to solve the KPG linear equation system of equations. To circumvent this problem, we made use of linear multiple regression analysis to find the main factors controlling the variation of receptor binding in a group of molecules. Statistics is used here as a slave and not as a master. Then, and from a philosophical point of view, this method is totally unrelated to those based on the equation: “*Any biological activity I want to study = a combination of all classical and quantum chemical parameters at my hand*” and using statistics to see if there is a statistically significant result.

Usually, the KPG method makes use of the concept of *common skeleton*. This skeleton is defined as a definite collection of atoms, common to all molecules selected for a study, which accounts for nearly all the receptor binding. The action of the substituents consists in modifying the electronic structure of the common skeleton and influencing the right alignment of the drug throughout the orientational parameters. Now, let us consider a molecular system depicted below.

This system is arbitrarily divided in regions A, B, C and D that are common to all molecules studied. The common skeleton contains atoms belonging to all of them. The standard KPG procedure employs this skeleton. Now, let us consider that case in which all molecules have regions A, B and C in common (set X), but region D is present only in some of them (set Y). In these cases the KPG method can be applied to two sets of molecules: the one corresponding to set X and the one composed by set X plus set Y. In the first case we use atoms of regions A, B and C to compose the common skeleton and in the second we employ atoms of the four regions. The analysis of the statistically significant results should provide more information about some of the atoms participating in the drug-receptor interaction. To test this approach, we present here the results of a study relating the electronic structure of some 2,5-dimethoxyphenethylamines and their *N*-2-methoxybenzyl-substituted analogs with 5-HT_{1A} serotonin receptors considering several definitions of the common skeleton. These molecules and receptor were selected because we carried out several studies on serotonin receptors and related molecules [23-30]. Another reason is that the molecules have psychoactive effects and it is of interest to compile information about their mode on binding to their receptors. Considering what we said above about the method we shall discuss in this paper only the results.

Calculations

The molecules and receptor binding results were taken from a recent publication [31], and are presented in Fig. 1 and Table 1. The binding affinities were measured in membrane preparations of human embryonic kidney (HEK) 293 cells overexpressing the 5-HT_{1A} receptors (human genes).

Figure 1: General formula of molecules used in this study

Table 1: 2,5-dimethoxyphenethylamines, their N-2-methoxybenzyl-substituted analogs and receptor binding.

Molecule	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R _N	log(K _i) 5HT _{1A}
1	OMe	H	Br	OMe	H	-0.62
2	OMe	H	Cl	OMe	H	-0.72
3	OMe	H	Me	OMe	H	-0.36
4	OMe	H	Et	OMe	H	-0.44
5	OMe	H	Br	OMe	2-methoxybenzyl	0.56
6	OMe	H	Cl	OMe	2-methoxybenzyl	0.70
7	OMe	H	Me	OMe	2-methoxybenzyl	0.85
8	OMe	H	Et	OMe	2-methoxybenzyl	0.54
9	OMe	H	H	OMe	H	-1.15
10	OMe	H	I	OMe	H	-0.74
11	OMe	H	NO ₂	OMe	H	0.34
12	OMe	H	<i>n</i> -Pr	OMe	H	-0.96
13	OMe	H	H	OMe	2-methoxybenzyl	0.78
14	OMe	H	I	OMe	2-methoxybenzyl	0.26
15	OMe	H	NO ₂	OMe	2-methoxybenzyl	0.62
16	OMe	H	<i>n</i> -Pr	OMe	2-methoxybenzyl	0.26
17	OMe	H	SEt	OMe	H	-0.43
18	OMe	H	<i>S-i</i> -Pr	OMe	H	-0.33
19	OMe	H	<i>S-Pr</i>	OMe	H	-0.28
20	H	OMe	OMe	OMe	H	0.66
21	OMe	H	SEt	OMe	2-methoxybenzyl	0.34
22	OMe	H	<i>S-i</i> -Pr	OMe	2-methoxybenzyl	0.40
23	OMe	H	<i>S-i</i> -Pr	OMe	2-methoxybenzyl	0.26
24	H	OMe	OMe	OMe	2-methoxybenzyl	1.32

The common skeleton

We considered four possibilities for the building of the common skeleton (see Fig. 1):

Case 1. We hypothesized that all 24 molecules interact with the 5HT_{1A} receptor only through the aromatic ring A, the alkylamino chain and the proton.

Case 2. We hypothesized that all 24 molecules interact with the 5HT_{1A} receptor only through the aromatic ring A, the alkylamino chain, the proton and the first atom of the substituents attached to positions 1-4.

Case 3. We hypothesized that all 12 *N*-2-methoxyphenyl-phenethylamines interact with the 5HT_{1A} receptor only through the aromatic ring A, the alkylamino chain, the proton, the first atom of the substituents attached to positions 1-4 and the methoxyphenyl moiety (including the first atom of the methoxyphenyl substituent).

Case 4. We hypothesized that all 12 phenylalkylamines interact with the 5HT_{1A} receptor only through the aromatic ring A, the alkylamino chain, the proton and the first atom of the substituents attached to positions 1-4 (see below for each common skeleton).

Calculations

The electronic structure of all molecules was calculated within the Density Functional Theory (DFT) at the mPW1PW91/DGDZVP level with full geometry optimization [32]. The protonated forms were used. The Gaussian suite of programs was used [33]. The information needed to calculate the numerical values for the LARIs was obtained from the Gaussian results with the D-Cent-QSAR software [34]. All the electron populations smaller than or equal to 0.01 e were considered as zero. Negative electron populations coming from Mulliken Population Analysis were corrected as usual [35]. Orientational parameters taken from published Tables or calculated as usual [36-38]. Since the resolution of the system of linear equations is not possible because we have not experimental

data, we employed Linear Multiple Regression Analysis (LMRA) techniques to find the best solution. For each case, a matrix containing the dependent variable ($\log(IC_{50})$ in this case) and the local atomic reactivity indices of all atoms of the common skeleton as independent variables was built. Regarding the local atomic reactivity indices depending on the MO (Fukui indices and superdelocalizabilities) we have employed only those associated with the frontier local molecular orbitals. The Statistica software was used for LMRA [39].

Results

Results for Case 1. The common skeleton for this case is shown below (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Common skeleton numbering for case 1

The best equation obtained was:

$$\log(IC_{50}) = 0.24 + 1.97S_7^N(LUMO)^* - 18.82S_8^E(HOMO)^* - 0.002S_1^N \quad (1)$$

with $n=21$, $R=0.98$, $R^2=0.96$, $\text{adj-}R^2=0.95$, $F(3,17)=121.93$ ($p<0.000001$) and $SD=0.13$. No outliers were detected and no residuals fall outside the $\pm 2\sigma$ limits. Here, $S_7^N(LUMO)^*$ is the nucleophilic superdelocalizability of the lowest vacant MO localized on atom 7, $S_8^E(HOMO)^*$ is the electrophilic superdelocalizability of the highest occupied MO localized on atom 8 and S_1^N is the total atomic nucleophilic superdelocalizability of atom 1. Tables 2 and 3 show the beta coefficients, the results of the t-test for significance of coefficients and the matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables of Eq. 1. There are no significant internal correlations between independent variables (Table 3). Figure 3 displays the plot of observed vs. calculated $\log(IC_{50})$.

Figure 3: Plot of predicted vs. observed $\log(K_i)$ values (Eq. 1). Dashed lines denote the 95% confidence interval

Table 2: Beta coefficients and t-test for significance of coefficients in Eq. 1

Var.	Beta	t(17)	p-level
$S_7^N(LUMO)^*$	0.85	16.19	<0.000001
$S_8^E(HOMO)^*$	-0.34	-5.32	<0.00006
S_1^N	-0.21	-3.18	<0.006

Table 3: Matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables in Eq. 1

	$S_7^N(\text{LUMO})^* S_8^E(\text{HOMO})^* S_1^N$		
$S_7^N(\text{LUMO})^*$	1		
$S_8^E(\text{HOMO})^*$	0.00	1	
S_1^N	0.02	0.35	1

The associated statistical parameters of Eq. 1 indicate that this equation is statistically significant and that the variation of the numerical values of a group of three local atomic reactivity indices of atoms of the common skeleton explains about 95% of the variation of $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$. Figure 3, spanning about 1.9 orders of magnitude, shows that there is a good correlation of observed *versus* calculated values and that almost all points are inside the 95% confidence interval. A very important point to stress is the following. When a local atomic reactivity index of an inner occupied MO (i.e., HOMO-1 and/or HOMO-2) or of a higher vacant MO (LUMO+1 and/or LUMO+2) appears in any equation, this means that the remaining of the upper occupied MOs (for example, if HOMO-2 appears, upper means HOMO-1 and HOMO) or the remaining of the empty MOs (for example, if LUMO+1 appears, lower means the LUMO) contribute to the interaction. Their absence in the equation only means that the variation of their numerical values does not account for the variation of the numerical value of the biological property.

Results for Case 2. The common skeleton for this case is shown below (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: Common skeleton numbering for case 2

The best equation obtained was:

$$\log(\text{IC}_{50}) = -1.59 + 2.08S_7^N(\text{LUMO})^* - 0.44S_3^E + 0.004S_4^N - 0.08\eta_{13} \quad (2)$$

with $n=24$, $R=0.96$, $R^2=0.93$, $\text{adj-}R^2=0.91$, $F(4,19)=58.742$ ($p<0.000001$) and $SD=0.20$. No outliers were detected and no residuals fall outside the $\pm 2\sigma$ limits. Here, $S_7^N(\text{LUMO})^*$ is the nucleophilic superdelocalizability of the lowest vacant MO localized on atom 7, S_3^E is the total atomic electrophilic superdelocalizability of atom 3 and η_{13} is the local atomic hardness of atom 13. Tables 4 and 5 show the beta coefficients, the results of the t-test for significance of coefficients and the matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables of Eq. 2. There are no significant internal correlations between independent variables (Table 5). Figure 5 displays the plot of observed *vs.* calculated $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$.

Table 4: Beta coefficients and t-test for significance of coefficients in Eq. 2

Var.	Beta	t(19)	p-level
$S_7^N(\text{LUMO})^*$	0.77	12.06	<0.000001
S_3^E	-0.40	-6.29	<0.000005
S_4^N	0.30	3.81	<0.001
η_{13}	-0.23	-2.87	<0.01

Table 5: Matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables in Eq. 2

	$S_7^N(\text{LUMO})^*$	S_3^E	S_4^N	η_{13}
$S_7^N(\text{LUMO})^*$	1			
S_3^E	0.02	1		
S_4^N	0.00	0.01	1	
η_{13}	0.00	0.00	0.35	1

Figure 5: Plot of predicted vs. observed $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$ values (Eq. 2). Dashed lines denote the 95% confidence interval. The associated statistical parameters of Eq. 2 indicate that this equation is statistically significant and that the variation of the numerical values of a group of four local atomic reactivity indices of atoms of the common skeleton explains about 91% of the variation of $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$. Figure 5, spanning about 2.5 orders of magnitude, shows that there is a good correlation of observed versus calculated values and that almost all points are inside the 95% confidence interval.

Results for Case 3. The common skeleton is shown below (Fig. 6).

Figure 6: Common skeleton numbering for case 3

The best equation obtained was:

$$\log(IC_{50}) = -1.73 - 11.94s_{11} + 0.18\eta_8 - 72.20S_{15}^E(\text{HOMO})^* \quad (3)$$

with $n=12$, $R=0.98$, $R^2=0.96$, $\text{adj-}R^2=0.94$, $F(3,8)=59.151$ ($p<0.00001$) and $SD=0.08$. No outliers were detected and no residuals fall outside the $\pm 2\sigma$ limits. Here, s_{11} is the local atomic softness of atom 11, η_8 is the local atomic hardness of atom 8 and $S_{15}^E(\text{HOMO})^*$ is the electrophilic superdelocalizability of the highest occupied MO localized on atom 15. Tables 6 and 7 show the beta coefficients, the results of the t-test for significance of coefficients and the matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables of Eq. 3. There are no significant internal correlations between independent variables (Table 7). Figure 7 displays the plot of observed *vs.* calculated $\log(IC_{50})$.

Table 6: Beta coefficients and t-test for significance of coefficients in Eq. 3

Var.	Beta	t(8)	p-level
s_{11}	-0.93	-12.12	<0.000002
η_8	0.49	6.434	<0.0002
$S_{15}^E(\text{HOMO})^*$	-0.19	-2.55	<0.03

Table 7: Matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables in Eq. 3

	s_{11}	η_8	$S_{15}^E(\text{HOMO})^*$
s_{11}	1		
η_8	0.06	1	
$S_{15}^E(\text{HOMO})^*$	0.01	0.01	1

Figure 7: Plot of predicted *vs.* observed $\log(IC_{50})$ values (Eq. 3). Dashed lines denote the 95% confidence interval. The associated statistical parameters of Eq. 3 indicate that this equation is statistically significant and that the variation of the numerical values of a group of three local atomic reactivity indices of atoms of the common skeleton explains about 94% of the variation of $\log(IC_{50})$. Figure 7, spanning about 1.2 orders of magnitude, shows that there is a good correlation of observed *versus* calculated values and that almost all points are inside the 95% confidence interval.

Results for Case 4. The common skeleton for this case is shown below (Fig. 8).

Figure 8: Common skeleton numbering for case 4

The best equation obtained was:

$$\log(IC_{50}) = 1.65 + 0.71S_2^N(LUMO)^* - 0.10\eta_{13} \quad (4)$$

with $n=12$, $R=0.88$, $R^2=0.85$, $\text{adj-}R^2=0.85$, $F(2,9)=33.247$ ($p<0.00007$) and $SD=0.19$. No outliers were detected and no residuals fall outside the $\pm 2\sigma$ limits. Here, $S_2^N(LUMO)^*$ is the nucleophilic superdelocalizability of the lowest vacant MO localized on atom 2 and η_{13} is the local atomic hardness of atom 13. Tables 8 and 9 show the beta coefficients, the results of the t-test for significance of coefficients and the matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables of Eq. 4. There are no significant internal correlations between independent variables (Table 9). Figure 9 displays the plot of observed vs. calculated $\log(IC_{50})$.

Figure 9: Plot of predicted vs. observed $\log(IC_{50})$ values (Eq. 4). Dashed lines denote the 95% confidence interval

Table 8: Beta coefficients and t-test for significance of coefficients in Eq. 4.

Var.	Beta	t(9)	p-level
$S_2^N(LUMO)^*$	0.81	6.93	<0.00007
η_{13}	-0.36	-3.12	<0.01

Table 9: Matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables in Eq. 4.

	$S_2^N(\text{LUMO})^* \eta_{13}$	
$S_2^N(\text{LUMO})^*$	1	
η_{13}	0.03	1

The associated statistical parameters of Eq. 4 indicate that this equation is statistically significant and that the variation of the numerical values of a group of two local atomic reactivity indices of atoms of the common skeleton explains about 85% of the variation of $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$. Figure 9, spanning about 2.0 orders of magnitude, shows that there is a good correlation of observed *versus* calculated values and that almost all points are inside the 95% confidence interval. Table 10 shows the local molecular orbitals of some atoms appearing in Eqs. 1-4. Nomenclature: Molecule (molecule's HOMO) / (HOMO-2)* (HOMO-1)* (HOMO)* - (LUMO)* (LUMO+1)* (LUMO+2)*.

Table 10: Local molecular orbitals of atoms 2, 7, 8 and 15

Molecule	Atom 2	Atom 7	Atom 8	Atom 15
1 π (66)	66 π -68 π	63 σ -67 σ	66 σ -67 σ	----
2 π (57)	57 π -59 π	52 σ -58 σ	57 σ -58 σ	----
3 (53)	53 π -55 π	52 σ -54 σ	53 σ -54 σ	----
4 (57)	57 π -59 π	56 σ -58 σ	57 σ -58 σ	----
5 (98)	98 π -101 π	93 σ -99 σ	98 σ -100 σ	94 σ -99 σ
6 (89)	89 π -92 π	81 σ -90 σ	89 σ -91 σ	85 σ -90 σ
7 (85)	85 π -88 π	84 σ -86 σ	84 σ -88 σ	82 σ -86 σ
8 (89)	89 π -92 π	88 σ -90 σ	89 σ -92 σ	86 σ -90 σ
9 (49)	49 π -51 π	48 σ -50 σ	48 σ -50 σ	----
10 π (75)	74 π -77 π	72 σ -76 σ	75 σ -76 σ	----
11 π (60)	60 π -61 π	54 σ -61 σ	56 σ -61 σ	----
12 π (61)	61 π -63 π	60 σ -62 σ	61 σ -62 σ	----
13 (81)	81 π -84 π	80 σ -84 σ	80 σ -82 σ	78 σ -82 σ
14 (107)	107 π -110 π	103 σ -110 σ	107 σ -108 σ	102 σ -108 σ
15 (92)	92 π -93 π	84 σ -93 σ	89 σ -93 σ	86 σ -94 σ
16 (93)	93 π -96 π	92 σ -96 σ	93 σ -94 σ	90 σ -94 σ
17 (65)	65 π -67 π	60 σ -66 σ	63 σ -66 σ	----
18 (69)	69 π -71 π	66 σ -70 σ	66 σ -70 σ	----
19 (69)	69 π -71 π	67 σ -70 σ	69 σ -70 σ	----
20 π (57)	57 π -59 π	57 σ -58 σ	57 σ -58 σ	----
21 π (97)	96 π -100 π	90 σ -100 σ	95 σ -98 σ	94 σ -98 σ
22 π (97)	96 π -100 π	90 σ -100 σ	95 σ -98 σ	93 σ -98 σ
23 (101)	101 π -104 π	98 σ -104 σ	101 σ -102 σ	97 σ -102 σ
24 (89)	89 π -92 π	84 σ -90 σ	89 σ -90 σ	85 σ -90 σ

Discussion

Discussion of Case 1.

The Beta values (Table 2) show that the importance of variables in Eq. 1 is $S_7^N(\text{LUMO})^* \gg S_8^E(\text{HOMO})^* > S_1^N$. The variable-by-variable (VbV) analysis of Eq. 1 shows that a high receptor affinity is associated with small values of $S_7^N(\text{LUMO})^*$ if this index has positive values, with small negative values of and with large positive values for S_1^N . Atom 7 is a carbon atom of the side chain ring (Fig. 2). Table 10 shows that all MOs have a σ nature. Table 10 also shows that the local HOMO₇* is located quite far below from the molecule's HOMO. Therefore, this MO is not very reactive. If $S_7^N(\text{LUMO})^*$ is positive, small values for this index are obtained by shifting upwards the energy of the

MO, making it less reactive (the same conceptual result is obtained if $S^N_7(\text{LUMO})^*$ is negative). This result can be understood in two main ways. The first one is that this atom is engaged in a weak C-H... σ^* dispersion interactions with the site using HOMO_7^* [40]. The other one is that $(\text{LUMO})_7^*$ could be engaged in a zero-electron repulsive interaction of the $\sigma^*-\sigma^*$ kind [41, 42]. Let us remember that σ electrons are found in the methanediyl groups of some amino acids. On the other hand, and because atom 7 is bonded to the phenyl ring, there is a third possibility to consider. If the phenyl ring is engaged in a parallel $\pi-\pi$ interaction with an aromatic moiety of the site but the rings are not exactly coincident among them, we may think in a C-H... π interaction [43]. What is really surprising is the role that this atom plays in regulating binding affinity. Note that all these interactions are weak. Atom 8 is the other carbon atom of the side chain, bonded to both, carbon atom 7 and nitrogen (Fig. 2). All its MOs have a σ nature (Table 10). In many cases but not all the local HOMO^* and LUMO^* coincide with the molecule's frontier MOs. $S^E_8(\text{HOMO})^*$ is always negative. Therefore, to get smaller values for this index we must shift downwards the energy of the associated eigenvalue, making this MO less reactive. This suggests that $(\text{HOMO})_8^*$ could be involved in a repulsive interaction with occupied MOs (of σ or π nature) of the site. Considering what we suggested about atom 7, it is more probable that this atom is also facing σ MOs. Atom 1 is a carbon atom of the aromatic ring (Fig. 2). This index is a scalar. High positive values for this index are obtained by lowering the empty MO energies, making this atom a good electron acceptor, probably from an occupied π MO of the receptor. Note that atom 1 is very close to atom 7. All the suggestions are displayed in the partial 2D pharmacophore of Fig. 10.

Figure 10: Partial 2D pharmacophore for Case 1

Discussion of Case 2

The Beta values (Table 4) show that the importance of variables in Eq. 2 is $S^N_7(\text{LUMO})^* \gg S^E_3 > S^N_4 > \eta_{13}$. A high affinity is associated with low (positive) values of $S^N_7(\text{LUMO})^*$, low (negative) values of S^E_3 , low (positive) values of S^N_4 and high (positive) values of η_{13} . Atom 7 is the carbon atom of the side chain bonded to the phenyl ring A (Fig. 4). The analysis of this index is exactly the same than for case 1. Atom 3 is a carbon atom in phenyl ring A (Fig. 4). Low negative values are obtained by shifting downwards the energy of the HOMO (having the main numerical contribution to this index), making it less reactive. Therefore we suggest that this atom is interacting with an electron-rich center of the receptor. This interaction can be of the $\pi-\pi$ or π -anion kinds but the fact that several atoms of ring A seem to interact with the receptor, a $\pi-\pi$ interaction is more probable. Atom 4 is a carbon atom of the phenyl ring A (Fig. 4). Low values for S^N_4 are obtained by shifting upwards the empty MO energies, making these MOs less reactive. For this reason we suggest that atom 4 is interacting with an electron deficient center in the receptor. As in the case of atom 3, this interaction should be probably of the $\pi-\pi$ kind (or π -cation). Atom 13 is the first atom of the R_3 substituent (Fig. 4). Table 1 shows that these substituents are of very different natures. High values of the *local* atomic hardness (η) of this atom are associated with high activity. η is defined as the $\text{HOMO}^*-\text{LUMO}^*$ gap [6]. Large values for this index are obtained by lowering the $(\text{HOMO})^*$ energy, rising the $(\text{LUMO})^*$ energy or by both procedures. Technically this can be done by finding substitutions changing the localization of these MOs, without varying the electronic structure of ring A. The different nature of this atom (Table 1) makes it

difficult to suggest possible interactions. For example: the H atom may be involved in CH...X hydrogen bond, the halogen ones in halogen H-bonds, etc. We think that, if there are any interactions, they must be weak ones. This is so because a high value of η_{13} shows that atom 13 seems to resist exchanging electrons with the surroundings. This suggests that atom 13 is possibly positioned close to a hydrophobic moiety (an alkyl chain for example). All the suggestions are displayed in the partial 2D pharmacophore of Fig. 11.

Figure 11: Partial 2D pharmacophore for Case 2

Discussion of Case 3

The Beta values (Table 6) show that the importance of variables in Eq. 3 is $s_{11} \gg \eta_8 \gg S_{15}^E(\text{HOMO})^*$. A high affinity is associated with high (positive) values of s_{11} , low (positive) values of η_8 and small (negative) values of $S_{15}^E(\text{HOMO})^*$. Atom 11 is the first atom of the R_1 substituent (Figs. 1 and 6, Table 1). s_{11} is defined as the inverse of η_{11} [6]. Therefore a high positive value of s_{11} is equivalent to a small positive value of η_{11} . Then, a high binding affinity is related to a small (HOMO)*-(LUMO)* energy gap. Then, atom 11 is prone to exchange electrons with an electron-deficient center of the receptor site. This is in agreement with the fact that in all but two molecules this atom is an oxygen one. Atom 8 is a carbon atom of the side chain linking ring A with the N atom (Fig. 6). Low values of η_8 are associated with a high affinity. All local MOs have a σ nature. This suggests that atom 8 is prone to exchange electrons with the environment. Unhappily, η is a scalar that does not give much information about the nature of this electron exchange, but we may guess that it could be engaged in σ - σ^* , σ^* - σ and/or CH...X weak interactions. Atom 15 is a carbon atom linking the side chain with ring B (Fig. 6). Small (negative) values of $S_{15}^E(\text{HOMO})^*$ are associated with a high receptor affinity. All local MOs have a σ nature. A low negative value for this index is obtained by lowering the value of the associated eigenvalue, making this MO less reactive. Therefore, we suggest that atom 15 is weakly interacting with the site through its lowest empty local MO. The interactions could be of the σ^* - σ , σ^* - π and/or C-H...X kinds. All the suggestions are displayed in the partial 2D pharmacophore of Fig. 12.

Figure 12: Partial 2D pharmacophore for Case 3

Discussion of Case 4

The Beta values (Table 8) show that the importance of variables in Eq. 4 is $S_2^N(\text{LUMO})^* \gg \eta_{13}$. A high affinity is associated with small values of $S_2^N(\text{LUMO})^*$ is this index is positive and with large values of η_{13} . Atom 2 is a carbon atom in ring A (Fig. 8). Large positive values are obtained by shifting downwards the energy of the associated eigenvalue, making this MO more reactive. Therefore, we suggest that atom 2 is interacting with an electron-rich center. Atom 13 is the first atom of the R_3 substituent (Fig. 8). Large values of this index are associated with high binding affinity. The discussion of this index is the same than for Case 2 (see above). All the suggestions are displayed in the partial 2D pharmacophore of Fig. 13.

Figure 13: Partial 2D pharmacophore for Case 4

Integration of Results

Figure 14 shows the integration of the results of the four cases in a single interaction partial pharmacophore.

Figure 14: Integrated 2D partial interaction pharmacophore

Unhappily, our results did not include local atomic reactivity indices of ring B. But we noticed that the presence of ring B helps to change the localization of some occupied and empty MOs. N-2-methoxybenzyl-substituted analogs have a lesser affinity than their 2,5-dimethoxyphenethylamines counterparts. Therefore, it would be interesting to change ring B by smaller substituents carrying π electrons. The results about the apparent modulation of the receptor affinity by the sp^3 carbon atoms of the side chain is surprising. If this fact is real, then substituting these three carbon atoms with methyl groups and measuring by separate the activity of all optical isomers is another interesting possibility to test.

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